

A Review on Factors Influencing Consumer Purchase Decision on Instagram

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Abstract – The rapid growth in the usage of social media has paved way to the marketers to engage with people easily. Instagram is the most scrolled social media platform compared to others, thus making it an attractive online venue to market products. This paper studies the influence of social media marketing on consumer's purchase decision. Brand trust, brand awareness, interaction and emotional attachment were the major influencing factors of the consumers purchase decisions. The objective of the paper is to study the relationship between the social media marketing and its influence on the consumers purchase decision. It is an empirical study, where the data is collected through a structured questionnaire and circulated through survey method. Purposive sampling method is used to collect data as the respondents are Instagram users. The paper concludes that, there is a positive relationship between brand trust, awareness and emotional attachment on consumers purchase decision on Instagram.

Keywords – Social media marketing, Purchase decision, Brand Trust, Instagram usage.

I. INTRODUCTION

Consumer purchase decision plays an important role in the market, as per the popular saying “Consumers are kings”. So consumer purchase decision can be explained as the path that begins when a customer realizes they possess a need, looks for solutions, evaluates their options, and finally decides on a specific product or service (Salem, 2018). As a result, the decision to buy can be understood as a sequence of actions that customers take prior to completing the purchase. It involves making decisions about what to buy, when to buy it, where to buy it, what brand or model to choose, how much to spend, and which payment method to employ.

Consumers' thoughts about a business's goods and their reputation are likely to influence their decision to buy. More specifically, customers' purchasing decisions are typically influenced by previous usage of a company's products and the degree to which the acquired item meets the needs at present (Hanaysha, 2022). The increasing use of social media, especially Instagram has attracted marketers to market and sell their products through these platforms. The fundamental basis for businesses adopting social media is gaining in power and in growing popularity (Gamboia & Gonçalves, 2014).

Few previous studies have looked at the various aspects of social media, which offer marketers incredible chances to connect with customers and establish reputation for their brands (Sohail et al., 2020). Due to social media's importance in influencing customer purchasing behavior, the use of these platforms for communicating and marketing new or current products or services has grown significantly in recent years (Park et al., 2021). Previous papers have studied the significance of social media marketing in relation to the purchase decision of the consumers. As there is a huge improvement in using

Instagram for purchasing products, this paper will study the influencing factors in determining the purchase decision of consumers on Instagram.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Hasan and Sohail (2020) has founded in his work that brand trust, brand awareness, brand community, interaction has a positive influence on the purchase decision of the consumer in online social media marketing. Alkharabsheh and Zhen (2021) has acknowledge that social media marketing has a relationship on the consumer buying decision process. Ardiansyah and Sarwoko (2020) has founded that social media marketing has a significant effect on brand awareness and social media marketing has a significant effect on the purchase decision of the consumers.

Hanaysha (2022) has explored the impact of social media marketing on purchase decision with brand trust as a mediation. He has founded that there is a significance in brand trust in predicting the purchase decision of consumers. Andrianti and Oetardjo (2022) has examined that digital marketing and brand awareness has a positive influence in the consumer purchasedecision. Mustikasari and Widaningsih (2019) has explored and concluded that the social media marketing has an increasing effect in the brand awareness and product buyingdecision.

Wu et al. (2015) has found that deep participation in the brand community has a positive effect on the purchase decision of the consumer. Jibril et al. (2019) has concluded that onlinebased brand community positively influences consumers trust and brand image. Nizam et al.(2018) has acknowledged that there is an impact on interaction and the consumer purchase decision in online advertisement marketing. Häubl and Trifts (2000) has founded that interactive aids have an impact in the consumers purchase decision. Ribeiro et al. (2022) hasconcluded that consumers

purchase decision is made after an online interaction of reviews, google ratings etc. Dar and Tariq (2021) has recommended that building a brands trust will improve the consumers purchase decision.

OBJECTIVES:

- To study the factors that influence the consumer’s purchase decision on Instagram.
- To study the relationship between the factors on consumer's purchase decision on Instagram.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study is empirical in nature, both primary and secondary data where to collect data. Primary data is collected using a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was developed using google forms and distributed around Chennai to get the results. 178 respondents were recorded by purposive sampling method as the respondents were Instagram users. The questionnaire constitutes demographic factors of the respondents followed by the variables that include brand trust, brand

awareness, interaction and emotional attachment that influence the purchase decision of the consumers on Instagram. Five point Likert scale was used to find the factors that influence the purchase decision of consumers on Instagram.

Secondary data was collected using journals, articles and websites for the study.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS

The data was analyzed using SPSS software (21st version). To attain the objectives of the study simple percentage analysis, descriptive statistics, correlation and regression analysis have been employed to determine and interpret the results of this study. Simple percentage analysis is used to study the demographic profile of the respondents; descriptive statistics were used to study the influencing factors of the consumer’s purchase decision. Correlation and Regression was employed to study the relationship among the factors of the consumer’s purchase decision on Instagram.

Table 1: Demographic Profile Of The Respondents

Simple Percentage analysis			
Variables	Factors	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	82	47.10%
	Female	92	52.90%
	Total	174	100%
Age	18 - 24	94	54.0%
	25 - 40	76	43.7%
	41 - 60	4	2.3%
	Total	174	100%
Educational Qualifications	Undergraduate	111	63.8%
	Postgraduate	53	30.5%
	Professional course	10	5.7%
	Total	174	100%
Family Monthly Income	Up-to 20,000	10	5.7%
	20,001 - 80,000	84	48.3%
	80,001 - 1,20,000	62	35.6%
	Above 1,20,000	18	10.3%
	Total	174	100%
Marital Status	Married	54	31.0%
	Unmarried	120	69.0%
	Total	174	100%
Frequency of Instagram use	Less than 1 hour	61	35.1%
	2 - 5 hours	101	58.0%
	5 -9 hours	12	6.9%
	Total	174	100%

Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics of the respondents. The data shows that the entire sample size is 174, with males comprising 82 and females contributing up

the majority of 92 in the population. The age group of 18 to 24 accounts for 54% of the sample total. The age groups of 25-40 and 40-60 make up 43.7% and 2.3% of the population

respectively. The respondents' educational backgrounds are classified as undergraduates (63.8%), postgraduates (30.4%), and professional courses (5.7%). It shows the respondents' monthly incomes are classified as up to 20,000, 20,001 - 80,000, 80,001 - 1,20,000, and above 1,20,000 at 5.7%, 48.3%, 35.6%, and

10.3%, respectively. From the table it is evident that the marital status of the respondents is classified into married 54 and unmarried 120. The frequency of the respondents who use Instagram are divided as less than one hour, 2 -5 hours, 5 - 9 hours which brings up to 61, 101 and 12 respectively.

TABLE 2: Model Summary, Anova and Coefficients

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square		Std. Error of the Estimate
Purchase Decision	.708 ^a	.502	.493	.51562	0.42365
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P - value
Regression	45.498	3	15.166	57.044	.000 ^b
Residual	45.197	170	.266		
Total	90.694	173			
Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t- value	P - value
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.081	.151		.536	.592
Brand Trust	.234	.084	.216	2.771	.006*
Brand Awareness	.192	.083	.171	2.310	.022*
Emotional Attachment	.420	.068	.431	6.175	.000*

Source: Computed Data

shows various factors that influence consumers' buying decisions on Instagram. From the R square value, we can identify that there is 50% influence in the study. Based on the results, we can conclude that brand trust has a positive correlation with customer purchasing decisions because the level of significance is less than 5%, which indicates that brand trust in a consumer makes him to purchase brands in Instagram. The results suggest that Brand Awareness has a positive correlation on consumer buying decisions, as the level of significance is less than 5%, supporting the alternate hypothesis. From this we can know that Users with brand awareness on the product will purchase products on Instagram. Emotional Attachment also influences consumers' purchasing decisions, with a significance level of less than 5%, People who are emotionally attached to the Instagram page of the brand will make them buy the products directly from Instagram. Even though Interaction has a strong relationship with the Consumer's purchase decision, but does not influence the people to buy brands from Instagram.

H1 – There is a positive relationship between Brand Trust and Consumer's purchase decision on Instagram.

H2 – There is a positive relationship Brand Awareness and Consumer's purchase decision on Instagram.

H3 - There is a positive relationship between Emotional Attachment and Consumer's purchase decision on Instagram.

V. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

From the study, we can understand that most of the respondents are Female (52.9%) that falls in the age group between 12 – 24 (54%). Most of the respondent's educational qualifications are undergraduates (63.8%) and their monthly family income lies between 20,001 – 80,000 (48.3%). The majority of the respondents are unmarried (69%) and the frequency of use in Instagram are 2 – 5 hours a day (58%). The other findings include that emotional attachment is the most influencing factors that determine the consumer's purchase decision on Instagram as the factor has the highest mean value among the other factors in influencing the consumer's purchase decision on Instagram. Following by Brand awareness and Brand trust which is ranked the second and third most influencing factor in determining the consumer's purchase decision on Instagram. Interaction is the least influencing factor that determine the consumer's purchase decision on Instagram.

From the study, it is evident that there is relationship between the factors that determine the consumer's purchase decision on Instagram. The correlation value is more than 50%, as they possess moderately strong relationship between them. From regression test, we can find that emotional attachment, brand awareness and brand trust have a positive correlation on the consumer's purchase decision on Instagram as the significance level is less than 5%. Thus from this results, we can accept the alternate hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis. Interaction has a strong linear relationship but does not influence the users to purchase brands in Instagram.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

The study findings indicate that consumer interaction represents the least influential factor in Instagram purchase decision-making. This presents a significant opportunity for brands to enhance their marketing effectiveness through targeted engagement strategies.

Interactive Content Strategies

Brands should prioritize developing dynamic content formats that foster two-way communication with consumers. Instagram Stories provide an ideal platform for implementing interactive elements such as polls, quizzes, and Q&A sessions. These features not only increase engagement metrics but also provide valuable consumer insights that can inform product development and marketing strategies.

Community Building Initiatives

Implementing strategic contests and giveaways can significantly boost consumer participation while expanding brand reach through user-generated content. These initiatives should be designed to encourage authentic interaction rather than superficial engagement, creating meaningful connections between brands and their target audiences.

Brand Storytelling Enhancement

Instagram Stories offer unique opportunities for authentic brand narrative development. Successful brands leverage this feature to share behind-the-scenes content, company values, and product development processes, creating emotional connections that translate into purchasing decisions.

Loyalty and Rewards Programs

Developing comprehensive rewards systems that recognize and incentivize user engagement can substantially improve interaction rates. These programs should reward various forms of participation, including likes, comments, shares, and user-generated content creation, thereby fostering community loyalty and encouraging repeat engagement.

Innovative Technology Integration

Implementing custom augmented reality (AR) filters and effects represents a cutting-edge approach to consumer engagement. These branded digital experiences not only enhance user interaction but also generate organic content sharing, effectively expanding brand visibility while creating memorable consumer experiences.

These strategic implementations can significantly enhance consumer interaction levels, ultimately contributing to improved brand recognition, increased sales conversion rates, and sustainable business growth through Instagram marketing channels.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This empirical investigation has comprehensively examined the primary determinants influencing consumer purchase decisions within the Instagram marketplace

ecosystem. The research framework, incorporating brand trust, brand awareness, emotional attachment, and interaction factors, builds upon established theoretical foundations while providing contemporary insights into social media commerce behavior (Hasan & Sohail, 2020).

Key Research Findings

The study demonstrates clear positive correlations between brand credibility, consumer awareness, and emotional connection with purchasing behavior on Instagram platforms. These findings underscore the critical importance of authentic brand representation and meaningful consumer relationship development in digital marketing strategies.

Future Research Directions

This study provides a foundation for understanding Instagram's role in consumer decision-making processes, while highlighting opportunities for further investigation into emerging social commerce trends and their impact on consumer behavior patterns.

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